

2
0
2
4

№ 5

Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy,
innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid
ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari

Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

Elektron nashr,
366 sahifa, dekabr, 2024-yil.

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Zokirova Nodira Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Shakarov Zafar G'afforovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, PhD

TAHRIR HAY'ATI:

Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor, akademik

Sharipov Kongratbay Avazimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Maxkamov Baxtiyor Shuxratovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shaumarov Said Sanatovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Turayev Bahodir Xatamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Allayeva Gulchexra Jalgasovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Arabov Nurali Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Maxmudov Odiljon Xolmirzayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Xamrayeva Sayyora Nasimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bobonazarova Jamila Xolmurodovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Irmatova Aziza Baxromovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bo'taboyev Muhammadjon To'ychiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shamshiyeva Nargizaxon Nosirxuja kizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor, TDIU kengash kotibi

Xolmuxamedov Muhsinjon Murodullayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Xodjayeva Nodiraxon Abdurashidovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Amanov Otabek Amankulovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Zikriyoyev Aziz Sadulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sxay Lana Aleksandrovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Norboev Odil Abraevich, Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi kafedrasida dosenti

Ismoilova Gulnora Fayzullayevna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Djumaniyazov Umrbek Ilxamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kasimova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kalanova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, dotsent

Ashurzoda Luiza Muxtarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Sardor Begmaxmat o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Botirali Roxataliyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor

Tursunov Ulug'bek Sativoldiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Bauyetdinov Majit Janizaqovich, Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti dotsenti, PhD

Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li, dotsent

Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil
28-avgustdagi 360/5-son
qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar
asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop
etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy
ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga
texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari
bo'yicha "Muhandislik va
iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga
kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz:

- Toshkent shahridagi G. V. Plexanov nomidagi Rossiya iqtisodiyot universiteti
- Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti
- Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalash muhandislari instituti" milliy tadqiqot universiteti
- Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti
- Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti
- Toshkent davlat transport universiteti
- Toshkent arxitektura-qurilish universiteti
- Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya universiteti
- Jizzax politexnika instituti

MUNDARIJA

Sanoat tarmoqlari raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlash jarayonlarini iqtisodiy-matematik modellash tirish.....	19
Tursunov Bekmuxammad Omonovich	
Yangi o'zbekistonda turmush tarzining shakllanishi va jamiyat taraqqiyotidagi o'rni.....	27
Axunov Muhammadamin Abduvasitovich	
Radiolokatsion uzatmalar yordamida gaz ballonli avtomobillar texnik ekspluatatsiyasini nazorat qilish.....	32
Mirzayev Bahodir Nuriddinovich, Zulfiqorova Guldon Akbarjon qizi	
Moliya tizimini barqarorlashtirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	37
Nazarov G'ayrat Xayrullayevich, Ollokulova Feruza Mansurovna	
Quyosh elektronikasida polikristallarning qo'llanilishi.....	42
Xoliqov Alimardon Sultonovich	
Статистический анализ производства плодоовощественной продукции в Республике Узбекистан.....	48
Анорбоева Бахтижамол Данияр қизи	
Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida "O'zbekneftgaz" aksiyadorlik jamiyatida innovatsion faoliyatni rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	57
Yuldoshev Sobir Fayzullaevich	
Raqamlashtirish va sanoat korxonalarining innovatsion salohiyatini statistik tahlil qilish.....	63
Jalolov Ilhomjon Isomiddinovich	
Пути развития фондового рынка на основе цифровых технологий.....	70
Шукурова Луиза Баратовна, Эшдавлатов Боймурод Соатович	
Mathematical model and analytical solutions of the process of physics-chemical hydrodynamics.....	76
Ismanova Klara Dulanbaevna	
Meva-sabzavot mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarish jaryonlarining ekonometrik va statistik tahlili.....	84
Jo'rayev Olim Albayevich	
O'zbekistonda raqamli iqtisodiyotni o'rni.....	91
Mardanaqulov To'liqin	
Studying the calculation process of gear geometry transmission in C++ and excel programs.....	95
Uzoqov Farxod G'afforovich	
Прогнозирование ожидаемых экономических изменений с корреляционно-регрессионного анализа (в примере: "NAFIS TEX GROUP" МСН).....	101
Уринов Адхамджан Акбарович	
Современные модели поведения промышленных предприятий в условиях привлечения инвестиций.....	106
Матчанов Умирзак Сейтжанович	
Управление инвестициями в развитие человеческого капитала как фактор повышения конкурентоспособности промышленных.....	112
Тилляходжаев А.А.	
алгоритмы принятия решений в управлении технологическими процессами подземного выщелачивания.....	119
Исманова Клара Дуланбоевна	

Kvant o'rali yarimo'tkazgichlarda optik yutilish koeffitsientini foton energiyasiga bog'liqligi.....	127
Sayidov Nozimjon Abdulnosirovich	
Malein kislota angidridini oksidlab oksiran olish.....	133
Muhiddinov Baxodir Faxriddinovich, Xamroyev Kamoliddin Shaxobiddinovich, Qiyomov Sharifjon Nizomovich, Xusanov S.Y.	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarini sug'urtalashning mintaqaviy xususiyatlari	138
Shuxrat Jalolidinovich Mamadjanov	
Jin mashinasining paxta tozalashdagi unumdorligini tahlil qilish va modellashtirish.....	144
Mirzakarimov Mirsharoffiddin Mirzaabdurahimovich	
Kichik biznesni moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash va ularni eksport salohiyatini oshirish.....	151
Daniyarov Kuvatbay Daurxanovich	
O'zbekiston ipoteka bozorida "ESKROU" tizimini joriy qilinishi.....	156
Abdullayev Muhammadsodiq Isroil o'g'li	
Korxonalarining moliyaviy-iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarini ekonometrik tahlili qilish masalalari.....	161
Jalilov Bahrom Sotiboldievich	
Noaniqlik sharoitida moliyaviy operatsiyalar narxini baholashning nazariy asoslari.....	166
Muradov Rustamjon Sobitxonovich	
Elektr transport vositalarining paydo bo'lish evolyutsiyasi va batareyalarning kamchiliklarini hal qilinishi kerak bo'lgan muammolari.....	171
Moydinov Dilyorbek Abidjanovich, Zokirjonov Azizbek Zokirjon o'g'li	
Maishiy xizmat ko'rsatish sohasining rivojlanishi.....	179
Israilov Rustam Ibragimovich	
Ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini baholash ko'rsatkichlari tizimi va baliqchilik tarmog'iga xos xususiyatlari.....	185
Aitimbetov Amirbek Qoishibekovich	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyati subyektlarida moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlarini qo'llash masalalari.....	189
Uzoqov Muhibillo Juraboevich	
Korporativ transformasiya sharoitida bank xizmatlarini takomillashtirishning ekonometrik tahlili.....	194
Baymuratova Madina Tursunboy qizi	
Iplarni turli muhitlarda namlikni o'zlashtirish ko'rsatkichlari	204
B.B.Mirzabaev, N.Yu.Sharibayev, B.T.Xolmurotov	
Un ishlab chiqarish korxonalarida donni sovuq konditsionerlash tizimining modellari va ularning tavsiflari.....	211
Akramova Gulhayo Abidovna, Yusupov Azamat Alijonovich	
Обоснование параметров ножа оборудования для резки плодоовощей.....	220
Худайбердиев Тохиржон Латифович	
Quritish usullarining zanjabil (zingiber officinale) ildizpoyasini kimyoviy tarkibiga ta'siri.....	226
Merganov Avazxon Turgunovich, Abdurasulov Abdurauf Xasanovich	
Sut bezi saraton kasalliklarini erta aniqlashda informativ belgilar majmuasini tanlash algoritmi	230
Nishanov Akhram Khasanovich, Mamajanov Rajmatilla Yakubjanovich, Xaidarov Sherali Islom o'g'li	
Vertical vibration analysis of conveyor with compound screw and belt bearing support.....	239
Marasulov Islombek Ravshanbek o'g'li	
Turkiston o'lkasidagi madrasalar holati XIX asr oxiri – XX asr boshlarida.....	250
Lukashova Natalya Mixaylovna	

Kichik biznes korxonalari tomonidan eksport mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarish konsepsiyasi.....	256
Boymirzayev Zokirjon Mashrabboyevich	
Qishloq joylar resurs salohiyatidan foydalanish samaradorligini baholashga uslubiy yondashuvlar	262
Tursunpo'latov Farxodjon Xoshimjon o'g'li	
Migratsiya jarayonlari va uni tadqiq etishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari.....	269
Abdullayeva Gulhayot Shuhratovna	
Personnel policies and crisis management: modifying hr tactics during pandemics or economic downturns.....	276
Sarimsakov Bakhtiyor Rakhmonjanovich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlari faoliyatini hukumat tomonidan moliya-kredit mexanizmi orqali qo'llab-quvvatlashning zaruriyati.....	280
Ergashev Otamurod Tashtemirovich	
Tijorat banklari reytingini aniqlashda aktivlar va kapital rentabelligi ko'rsatkichlarining tahlili	287
Maxmudov Omon Tuxtayevich	
Автоматизированная система эффективное управление перекрестками дорог для транспортных средств	292
Мамаджанов Рахматилла Якубджанович, Алиев Махмуд Муса оглы, Холбоев Алишер Бобохон оглы	
Роль железнодорожного транспорта в сфере туризма и развитие туризма в центральной азии	298
Мухамедова Ситора	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida tijorat banklari faoliyatini transformasiyalashni takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	304
I.A. Yuldashev	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarida innovatsion loyihalarni ekspertizadan o'tkazish mexanizmini takomillashtirish orqali innovatsion faoliyat samaradorligini oshirish.....	310
Ibrohimov Boburmirzo Baxtiyor o'g'li	
Tijorat banklari depozit operatsiyalarining bugungi kundagi holati hamda uni takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	317
Shamsiyev Nodir Muratovich	
Современное состояние демографического развития регионов Узбекистана	325
Цхай Лана Александровна	
Qurilish materiallar sanoatida klaster tizimidan foydalanishning xususiyatlari	335
Utarov Doniyorbek G'ayratbek o'g'li, Saidov Mash'al Samadovich	
Исследование состава, физико-химических и эксплуатационных свойств битумов.....	339
Хужакулов Азиз Файзуллаевич, Абдуллаева Шохиста Шухратовна	
Sanoat korxonalarining moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlash	344
Yuldashev Fozil Turapovich	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan kredit operatsiyalarining iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish mexanizmlari	350
Djumaniyazov Ikram Karimbayevich	
Umumta'lim muassasalari xarajatlarini moliyalashtirish choralari	355
Ummatov Avaz Muydinovich	
The production potential of developing agriculture in mountain and foothill areas.....	360
Abdul Khaeva Gulshan Makhmudovna	

THE PRODUCTION POTENTIAL OF DEVELOPING AGRICULTURE IN MOUNTAIN AND FOOTHILL AREAS

Abdul Khaeva Gulshan Makhmudovna

Associate professor of tourism department of Termiz state university

Abstract: This article is devoted to the production potential of mountainous and highland regions related to the development of agriculture. In this study, economic and ecological characteristics of mountain and sub-mountain regions, available resources for agriculture and methods of their effective use are analyzed. In addition, the article examines the new directions of production necessary to increase the agricultural potential in these regions. Research results play an important role in effective organization of agricultural production in the region, rational use of resources and economic development. The article also provides recommendations and strategic directions for creating new jobs for local residents, strengthening agricultural infrastructure, and ensuring environmental sustainability.

Keywords: mountain regions, foothill regions, agriculture, production potential, ecological stability, rational use of resources, innovative methods, economic development, agro-infrastructure, jobs, efficient production, regional development, agricultural infrastructure.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola qishloq xo'jaligini rivojlantirish bilan bog'liq tog' va tog'oldi hududlarning ishlab chiqarish salohiyatiga bag'ishlangan. Ushbu tadqiqotda tog' va tog'oldi hududlarning iqtisodiy va ekologik xususiyatlari, qishloq xo'jaligi uchun mavjud resurslar va ulardan samarali foydalanish usullari tahlil qilinadi. Bundan tashqari, maqolada ushbu hududlarda qishloq xo'jaligi salohiyatini oshirish uchun zarur bo'lgan yangi ishlab chiqarish yo'nalishlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Ilmiy tadqiqot natijalari viloyatda qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqarishini samarali tashkil etish, resurslardan oqilona foydalanish va iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Shuningdek, maqolada mahalliy aholi uchun yangi ish o'rinlari yaratish, qishloq xo'jaligi infratuzilmasini mustahkamlash va ekologik barqarorlikni ta'minlash bo'yicha tavsiyalar va strategik yo'nalishlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tog'li hududlar, tog'oldi hududlar, qishloq xo'jaligi, ishlab chiqarish salohiyati, ekologik barqarorlik, resurslardan oqilona foydalanish, innovatsion usullar, iqtisodiy rivojlanish, agroinfratuzilma, ish o'rinlari, samarali ishlab chiqarish, hududiy rivojlanish, qishloq xo'jaligi infratuzilmasi.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена производственному потенциалу горных и предгорных регионов, связанному с развитием сельского хозяйства. В данном исследовании анализируются экономические и экологические характеристики горных и предгорных регионов, имеющиеся ресурсы для сельского хозяйства и методы их эффективного использования. Кроме того, в статье рассматриваются новые направления производства, необходимые для увеличения сельскохозяйственного потенциала в этих регионах. Результаты исследований играют важную роль в эффективной организации сельскохозяйственного производства в регионе, рациональном использовании ресурсов и развитии экономики. В статье также даются рекомендации и стратегические направления по созданию новых рабочих мест для местных жителей, укреплению сельскохозяйственной инфраструктуры и обеспечению экологической устойчивости.

Ключевые слова: горные регионы, предгорные регионы, сельское хозяйство, производственный потенциал, экологическая устойчивость, рациональное использование ресурсов, инновационные методы, экономическое развитие, агроинфраструктура, рабочие места, эффективное производство, региональное развитие, сельскохозяйственная инфраструктура

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is an important sector in the economic development of every country. Especially the mountain and sub-mountainous regions, with their natural resources and climatic conditions, have great production potential for agriculture. Economic activity in these areas is often shaped by interrelated environmental, social, and economic factors. However, the agricultural development potential of mountain and sub-mountain regions is often limited by specific geographical and climatic conditions, as well as technical and technological aspects.

This article is aimed at studying the production potential of mountain and sub-mountain regions in the development of agriculture. The research examines the problems and opportunities in agriculture in these regions, effective use of resources, and ways to ensure environmental sustainability and economic development. The analyzes in the article include proposals and recommendations necessary to increase the agricultural development potential of mountain and sub-mountain regions.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

It is important to rely on various literature in studying the production potential related to the development of agriculture in mountain and sub-mountain areas. Research on this topic often covers ecological, agrotechnical and economic aspects. There are many scientific works on resource efficiency, technological innovation and environmental sustainability in agricultural development.

A noteworthy aspect of the research of Z.M.Akramov and O.Otamirzaev¹, one of the leading scientists from Uzbekistan, is that in their research, the mountainous regions of Uzbekistan were divided into two - mountain and sub-mountain regions. In this, the main attention is focused on natural conditions, resources, some aspects and characteristics of the agricultural sector in these regions. In our opinion, this is the most positive and noteworthy aspect of these studies. However, they are limited only to the analysis of crop area and production volume, the methodological and normative bases of determining the boundaries of mountain and sub-mountain regions are recognized in general, and the agriculture of mountain and sub-mountain regions is not considered as a system.

It should be noted that in the studies related to the development of agriculture in mountain and sub-mountain areas, soil formation, water sources (streams and springs) and their use, plant and climate resources, environmental although the issues of development of dry farming, horticulture, viticulture and animal husbandry have been researched, this process is fragmented, leading to different disciplines and specializations and directions of goals.² Also, not only leading scientists of our country, but also foreign scientists C.A. Gashkina studied the organizational and economic mechanisms of sustainable development of agriculture in mountain regions, while³ A.E. In Maltsev's scientific research, the use of land and water resources in irrigated and dry farming, the influence of natural conditions on pastures and hayfields, and their characteristics were analyzed⁴

1 Otamirzaev.O. Tukhliev N. Uzbekistan: nature, population, economy. - T.: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2009.

2 Palmin B.A. and others. Problems of agricultural development of mountains and foothills of Uzbekistan. Publ. "Fan" of the Uzbek SSR. Tashkent-1969. - p. 449. Dogeev.G.D., Serderov V.K., Khanbabaev T.G. Current state and priorities for the development of mountainous territories of the region.//In the monograph "Organizational and economic mechanism for efficient potato seed production in Dagestan". Makhachkala, 2020. – 161 p. Khanbabaev T.G. Scientific, innovative and technological foundations of modernization of mountain agriculture (monograph). Republic of Dagestan - DNIISKH named after F.G. Kisriev. 2016. pp. 27-43.

3 Gashkina. S.A. "Organizational and economic mechanism of sustainable development of agriculture in mountain regions (on the example of the Altai Republic). Krasnoobsk – SNIESH. 2007 p. 215.

4 Maltsev. A.E. Land and water resources of Central Asia and their agricultural use. Frunze — Ilm Publishing House, 1969. 99 p.

These regions are considered as a special scientific direction for agricultural economic practice. In fact, although the characteristics of mountain and sub-mountain agricultural production have been considered in the scientific research of a number of scientists, today as a special research object, the theory of agricultural economics and economy is one of the important issues in management practice. Therefore, these issues are manifested in the vital and economic interests of the country, as well as in the lifestyle of the inhabitants of the region, interstate economic relations and integration relations. Therefore, it is necessary to generalize the results of the researches conducted on mountain regions in various fields of science, and to develop scientific recommendations for the development of mountain and sub-mountain agriculture.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, methods such as abstract thinking, systematic approach, and complex evaluation were used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

67 (42.1 percent) districts of 9 regions, which are part of the mountain and sub-mountain regions of the country, have a great role and importance in strengthening the food independence of our republic and stabilizing the food supply to the population. 46.5% of gross agricultural products grown in our republic are produced in these areas, including 45.6% of livestock products and 47.2% of agricultural products. Agricultural products make up 54.0% of the gross agricultural product grown in the mountainous and sub-mountainous regions of the republic, and livestock products make up 46.0%.

In the republic, 46.0 percent of cereal crops, 53.0 percent of potato cultivation areas, and 63-70 percent of fruit and grape areas are located in mountainous and highland regions, respectively. 40.0 percent of grain, 55.0 percent of potatoes, 51.0 percent of fruit and grape cultivation areas, and 67.0 percent of fruit and grape cultivation areas are grown in these areas. More than 48.0 percent of exported fruit and vegetable products (even more for some types of products) fall on the share of mountainous and highland regions.

In mountain and mountainous regions, grain is 3.0 percent, potatoes 1.5 times, vegetables 1.3 times, fruit 1.4 times, grapes 1.8 times, meat per capita. and milk is produced 1.3 times more. As of 2023, 76 kilograms of grain (38%), 48 kilograms of potatoes (55%), 138 kilograms of vegetables (46.5%), 41.5 kilograms of fruit (51%) are grown per capita in the republic. 32 kilograms (66.7%) of grapes, 33 kilograms (45%) of meat, 137 kilograms (43%) of milk and honey 16 kilograms (42.1%) of mountain and sub-mountain regions are accounted for by agriculture.

As a result of measures taken to ensure the innovative development of the agricultural sector of regions and regions in the republic and the creation of a favorable investment environment, the share of mountain and sub-mountain regions in the country's agriculture is increasing year by year.

The most notable and unique aspect is that these indicators have shown stability and have a growing trend in recent years. If we take into account that 3/2 of the fruits and vegetables, dairy and meat products grown for the population's consumption, as well as agricultural products and raw materials for the industrial and processing industry are created in these areas, then their country's food security and It is more evident that the role and importance in ensuring social and economic development is high.

The Surkhandarya oasis is one of the regions that is distinguished by the large number of days with high temperature compared to other regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, with a significant share of mountain and sub-mountain regions.⁵

The total land area of mountain and sub-mountain areas in the region is 20.1 mln. It is 18.1 million hectares or 90.0 percent of the land area. 10 out of 14 administrative districts of the region (71.4 percent) belong to the category of mountain and sub-mountain regions.

5 Abdulkhayeva.G. Main Directions For Development of Sewerage Regions of Mountainous and Bounded Territo.// International Journal of Research in Management & Business Studies. IJRMB 2019. P.55- 58. (Global Impact Factor 0.705)

The oasis mountain and sub-mountain regions have a large land base and favorable natural climatic conditions, as well as significant agricultural land. 76.0% of irrigated agricultural land, 98.0% of hayfields and pastures, and 82.0% of forests are located in mountain and sub-mountain areas⁶. 92.2% of the agricultural land, as well as 97.9% of the hayfields and pastures in the districts included in the mountain and mountain regions of the region are owned by farmers and peasants (private estates) and other agricultural enterprises.

One of the factors describing the current state of agriculture in mountain and sub-mountain regions is the number of people and labor resources in these regions, as well as the availability of qualified personnel. Because, if the diversification of the industry reduces the level of labor migration, the availability of qualified workers allows to create jobs with high scientific and intellectual labor capacity in the field, increasing the level of automation and mechanization of agrotechnical activities and processes in agriculture. serves to create high-value jobs in the countryside.

It is known that the formation of labor resources is inextricably linked with the general and natural growth rate of the population, and due to the observation of a specific mentality and the low level of urbanization, the population of mountain and sub-mountainous regions is steadily increasing compared to the population of plain regions. shows a growing trend (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Main demographic indicators of mountainous and foothill areas of the Surkhandarya region, in percentages⁷.

Analyses show that in 2023, 67.3 percent of the total population of the region's mountainous and foothill regions will live in the foothill regions, and 12.4 percent in the mountainous regions, and a high growth trend in the number of people living in the foothill regions has been observed over the past decade (Figure 1).

Therefore, in 2015-2023, the share of dehqan (private subsidiary) farms in the composition of agricultural products produced in mountainous and foothill regions grew rapidly, reaching 77.2% in 2023 from 31.7% in 2015.

In 2015, agricultural products accounted for 42.3 percent and livestock products for 57.7 percent of the total agricultural output produced in mountainous and foothill regions, while in 2023 this figure was 54.3 and 45.7 percent, respectively, i.e., the share of agricultural products increased by 12 percentage points during the analyzed period (Figure 2).

⁶ State Committee of Land Resources, Geodesy, Cartography and State Cadastre of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent – 2016-y.

⁷ It was compiled based on the information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Figure 2. Sectoral composition of agricultural products in mountainous and foothill districts of Surkhandarya region, in percentages to the total⁸.

This is explained by the increase in agricultural production due to the optimization of cotton cultivation areas in mountainous and foothill regions, the expansion of arable land allocated for grain crops, vegetable growing, horticulture, and viticulture as a result of the reforms being carried out in the country's agrarian sector.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The results of the study showed that mountainous and highland regions have great production potential for agricultural development. The natural resources and climatic conditions in these areas provide favorable opportunities for agriculture, but there are many factors to their effective use. In particular, in order to achieve high efficiency, the introduction of modern agrotechnologies, innovative methods and directions based on rational use of resources are important. Also noteworthy are issues of environmental sustainability and job creation for local residents.

To increase the agricultural production potential of these regions, it is necessary to solve environmental and economic problems, introduce new agricultural technologies, and effectively use local resources. It is also important to emphasize that it is important to strengthen cooperation between the public and private sectors to strengthen agricultural infrastructure, develop the agricultural sector, and implement innovative projects.

List of used literature

1. Abdulkhaeva.G. Main Directions For Development of Sewerage Regions of Mountainous and Bounded Territo.// International Journal of Research in Management & Business Studies. IJRMBS 2019. P.55- 58. (Global Impact Factor 0.705)
2. Abdulkhaeva.G. M "Development of the market of agricultural products by supporting the economic activity of women's entrepreneurship in mountainous and sub-mountainous regions". Actual tasks of the effective use of modern marketing concepts in the development of the national economy. Collection of scientific articles and abstracts of the International Scientific Practical Conference. (October 25, 2022). - T .: TSUE, 2022. (Volume 2) - 527 pages.
3. Abdulkhaeva, G. (2022). Mountain and sub-mountain areas are the main directions of agricultural development. Scientific progress, 3(2), 313-322.

⁸ It was compiled based on the information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

4. Abdulkhaeva, G. M. (2020). Foreign experience of innovative development of mountain and sub-mountain agriculture. *Innovation in Economics*, 3(3).
5. Abdulkhaeva, G., & Bobokulov, Sh. (2022). Top directions of state support in the development of agriculture in mountain and sub-mountain regions. *Scientific progress*, 3(1), 570-578.
6. Durmanov, A., Bartosova, V., Drobyazko, S., Melnyk, O., & Phillipov, V. (2019). Mechanism to ensure sustainable development of enterprises in the information space. *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, 7 (2), 1377–1386. <https://doi.org/10.2478/2541-8653.100000191>
7. Durmanov, AS, Tillaev, AX, Ismayilova, SS, Djamalova, XS, & Murodov, SM ogli. (2019). Economic-mathematical modeling of optimal level costs in the greenhouse vegetables in Uzbekistan. *Espacios*, 40 (10).

Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2024. № 5

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

